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IEWS OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: *This article presents the results of a study devoted to the consideration of various approaches to the professional competence of foreign language teachers in non-linguistic universities, such concepts as "competence" and "competence", "linguistic competence", "communicative competence", "psychological and pedagogical competence", "pedagogical culture", "terminological competence", "cross-cultural competence" in relation to the sphere of higher education.*

Keywords: *competence, competence, linguistic competence, psychological and pedagogical competence, pedagogical culture, terminological competence.*

Introduction

The relevance of the problem considered in the work is due to the fact that the professional competence of foreign language teachers is a complex phenomenon integrating such professionally significant characteristics as linguistic competence, communicative competence, psychological and pedagogical competence, pedagogical culture, cross-cultural competence and terminological competence in relation to the sphere of higher education.

The aim of the work was to consider various approaches related to the formation and development of professional competence of foreign language teachers in non-linguistic universities, including such professionally significant characteristics as linguistic competence, communicative competence, psychological and pedagogical competence, pedagogical culture, terminological competence and cross-cultural competence in relation to the sphere of higher education.

Materials and methods

The study considers approaches to the study of professionally significant characteristics of foreign language teachers of non-linguistic universities from the point of view of their formation and manifestation in practical activities. The scientific, scientific and methodological literature and documentation devoted to the processes of professionalization of higher education teachers were studied.

Results

The analysis of scientific and scientific and methodological literature, the authors' own professional activities, interaction with experienced teachers allow us to say that at present considerable attention is paid to the formation and development of professional competence of higher education teachers in general. Of particular interest are works related to the formation and development of

motivation for scientific activity, as well as psychological and pedagogical competence of teachers in organizing educational and extracurricular activities. However, attention is drawn to the insufficient elaboration of the issue of the complex of competencies that make up the general professional competence of foreign language teachers in non-linguistic universities, which certainly has its own specifics and features of formation and development.

A significant aspect of our work was the study of concepts that are used in the area we are studying.

It has been established that the concept of "competence" means awareness, knowledge, understanding in a particular area. In modern methodological science, "competence" means a set of knowledge, skills and abilities. In addition to the term "competence", the term "competence" is also used. These concepts are distinguished: competence is a set of knowledge, skills, abilities acquired during classes, competence is the properties of an individual that determine his or her ability to perform activities based on the formed competence [6, p. 142].

Linguistic (language) competence is the possession of a system of information about the studied language at its levels: phonemic, morphemic, lexical, syntactic. The teacher must know the system of a foreign language (language structure, language grammar, phonetic structure, historical aspects of a foreign language) and must be able to apply this in practice. The term "linguistic competence" was first introduced by the American linguist N. Chomsky in the mid-20th century.

An analysis of scientific and methodological literature has shown that communicative competence is the leading one in modern foreign language teaching methods. The concept of "communicative competence" is a set of knowledge about the language system, its units, their construction and functioning in speech, about the ways of formulating thoughts in the studied language and understanding the judgments of others, about the national cultural characteristics of the speakers of the studied language, the ability to communicate in various types of speech activity in accordance with the communicative tasks being solved.

According to the definition of D. Hymes, "communicative competence" is an internal knowledge of the situational appropriateness of language, as an ability that allows one to be a participant in speech activity [3, p. 180].

Of course, general foreign language competence is one of the most significant characteristics of a foreign language teacher in a non-linguistic university. At the same time, foreign language communicative competence, according to domestic researchers (I.L. Bim, N.D. Galskova, R.P. Milrud, V.V. Safonova, etc.), is the ability and readiness for foreign language communication with native speakers, perception and understanding of partners, adequate and timely expression of one's mental intentions.

Interaction with experienced teachers makes it possible to assert that general pedagogical competence has a significant impact on the success of the teacher's professionalization process. At the same time, in scientific and methodological works, the pedagogical competence of a teacher is considered as a set of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary to perform the function of teaching and educating students. This competence includes the following pedagogical knowledge: subject, basic concepts and objectives of the discipline "Pedagogy and Psychology of Higher Education"; goals, content, state educational standard and principles of constructing the content of higher professional education; the essence and patterns of the learning process; methods and organizational forms of teaching and educating students; modern pedagogical technologies.

Effective interaction with students is determined by the psychological and pedagogical competence of the teacher. The psychological competence of the teacher means the following system of knowledge: psychology of educational and cognitive activity of students; psychology of personality; psychological characteristics of students; psychology of the student body; fundamentals of psychodiagnostics; psychology of the pedagogical activity of the teacher; psychology of pedagogical communication.

Psychological and pedagogical skills represent a set of various actions of the teacher that are related to the functions of pedagogical activity [5, p. 74].

An important role is played by the pedagogical culture of the teacher, which consists of his personal qualities, such as dedication, love for students, interest in the development of their individuality, creativity, loyalty to his calling, i.e., in general, the personal potential of the teacher in conjunction with the quality of his professional training: psychological and pedagogical, subject. It can be concluded that the higher the level of pedagogical culture of the teacher, the more successful he is in his professional activity [4, p. 13].

In addition, the teacher should take into account such a concept as "cross-cultural" competence. Cross-cultural competence is defined as the process of teaching a new culture, its language, types of behavior in order to understand people of this culture, to feel sympathy for them and to successfully live and interact with them. An effective means of forming the development of socio- and cross-cultural competence of students is the use of authentic materials, elements of national culture and personal communicative experience in the process of teaching intercultural communication.

A large number of graduates of non-linguistic universities communicate in a foreign language in the course of their professional activities, participate in international conferences, cooperate with foreign companies. In this regard, teaching a foreign language is a relevant and important element in a non-linguistic university. Proficiency in oral and written speech in a foreign language for professional purposes becomes a need for a specialist in any field of knowledge [2, p. 153].

Speaking about teaching a foreign language in medical schools, the teacher must be competent in this area: have basic knowledge of human anatomy and physiology, knowledge of medical vocabulary, and the basics of the Latin language. Medical topics are an area where approximate formulations or inaccurate terms are unacceptable, otherwise this may cause inaccurate diagnostics and even medical errors. In this case, a significant role is given to the teacher's focus on self-education and self-improvement. The most important component of teaching a foreign language in a medical school is the study of specialized scientific terminology. Scientific terminology is very diverse and causes difficulties in translation. In this case, interaction with teachers of specialized disciplines allows the teacher to better understand the practical application of terminology and scientific medical concepts. Moreover, one of the most difficult to translate is the category of words, namely, "false friends of the translator". According to K.G. Gottlieb defines "false friends of the translator" as words of two (possibly several) languages that, due to the similarity of their form and content, can cause false associations, which leads to an erroneous perception of information in a foreign language, and when translated - to distortions of content, errors in lexical compatibility, inaccuracies in the transmission of stylistic coloring [1, p. 76]. Examples include such words as: angina, gland, complexion, insult, physician, sodium.

In addition, a teacher at a medical school should take into account the use of such an aspect as eponyms, which are one of the most numerous layers of medical terminology. Eponyms are divided into the following groups: mythologisms; biblicalisms; terms including the names of literary

characters; terms including the names of scientists and doctors; terms including the names of patients. For example, an eponym included in the group of terms including the names of scientists and doctors is Botkin's disease (hepatitis A). Hepatitis is a large group of inflammatory liver diseases. The most common of them, hepatitis A (often called jaundice or "disease of dirty hands"), is named after the Russian scientist and doctor Sergei Petrovich Botkin.

Conclusions

Thus, consideration of the issue of competence of foreign language teachers in a non-linguistic university requires careful consideration of such concepts as "competence" and "competence", and above all, linguistic competence, communicative competence, psychological and pedagogical competence, pedagogical culture, terminological competence, cross-cultural competence. It is quite obvious: in order to perform their work with high professionalism, a teacher must possess not only all of the above-mentioned general linguistic and psychological and pedagogical competencies, but must also have a high level of proficiency in specialized medical and biological and clinical terminology, as well as competence in the field of a given university and the main narrow specialties and areas. Terminological competence also implies proficiency in special terms related to the group of "false friends of a translator" in relation to the medical sphere and eponyms, which reflect not only certain medical concepts, but also have special educational significance.

LITERATURE

1. Borisova L.I. False friends of the translator. Moscow: NVITEsaurus, 2005. 211 p.
2. Gavrilenko N.N. The role of translation in the process of training non-linguistic specialists // Bulletin of the Moscow State Linguistic University. 2013. No. 12. P. 153161.
3. Gez N.I., Frolova G.M. History of foreign methods of teaching foreign languages. Moscow: Academy, 2008. 256 p.
4. Golovash I.I. Professional culture of a teacher in the context of social changes, global problems of society. // Collection "Personality Potential". - Kurgan, 2010. - P. 13.
5. Sharipov F.V., Ufa State Aviation Technical University // Professional competence of a university teacher. P. 74
6. Shchukin A.N. Methods of Teaching Russian as a Foreign Language: a textbook for universities / A.N. Shchukin. - M.: Higher. school, 2003. - 332 p.
7. Tuychievna R. L., Kamilla E. EFFECTIVENESS OF IMPROVING MENTAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 05. – C. 73-80.
8. Tuychievna R. L. PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF STUDENTS'INTELLECTUAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2023. – T. 12. – C. 38-54.
9. Tuychiyevna R. L. Phenomenon of Professional Stress in Pedagogical Activities of the Higher Education System //International Journal of Scientific Trends. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 73-78.
10. Obloberdiyevna D. S., Tuychiyevna R. L. Distance learning in the system of higher education. Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal, 1 (4), 53–59.

11. Tuychiyevna R. L. Norms and Requirements for Communication in the Teacher-Student System //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 3. – С. 214-218.
12. Tuychiyevna R. L., Navruza M. Importance of National Culture and Tradition in the Development of Psychological Characteristics //Web of Semantics: Journal of Interdisciplinary Science. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 193-197.
13. Tuychiyevna R. L. THE STRUCTURE AND CONTENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE SPEECH IN AN INTERACTIVE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT //International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development. – 2023. – Т. 10. – №. 11.
14. Tuychiyevna R. L. IMPROVEMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS'COMMUNICATIVE SPEECH //International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development. – 2023. – Т. 10. – №. 11.
15. Maxsidin o'g'li N. F. UMUMTA'LIM O'QUVCHILARINI IJTIMOIIY KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INTERFAOL TA'LIM METODLARINING AHAMIYATI //Uzbek Scholar Journal. – 2022. – Т. 5. – С. 215-218.
16. Maxsidin o'g'li N. F. MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARINING IJTIMOIIY-MADYANIY KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH //Uzbek Scholar Journal. – 2022. – Т. 5. – С. 219-221.
17. Maqsidtin o'g'li N. F., Shuhratova A. F. GROUPING OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES ACCORDING TO THE DEGREE OF DEVELOPMENT OF MENTAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE INDIVIDUAL //Academia Repository. – 2024. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 292-299.
18. Norbo'tayev F. M., Shuhratovna A. F. THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING SOCIAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS DURING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – Т. 7. – С. 9-17.
19. Норботаев Ф.М., Имомова Л.З. ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПЕРСОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ I У ШКОЛЬНИКОВ-МОЛОДЕЖИ //Журнал инноваций, реформ и развития «Спектр». – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 187-191.
20. Норботаев Ф.М., Ш.А.Ф. РОЛЬ, СУЩНОСТЬ И КРИТЕРИИ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕНСАЦИИ СТУДЕНТОВ //Журнал инноваций, реформ и развития «Спектр». – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 177-181.
21. Ходжиева Ф. О., Норботаев Ф. М. Пути развития критического мышления подростков //international scientific review of the problems and prospects of modern science and education. – 2018. – С. 78-79.
22. Норботаев Ф.М., Фаттоева М.Ю. НАУЧНО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕНСАЦИИ У СТУДЕНТОВ //Журнал инноваций, реформ и развития «Спектр». – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 192-196.
23. Норботаев Ф.М., Шухратовна А.Ф. ПРОЦЕСС ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ В ВО ВРЕМЯ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА //Журнал инноваций, реформ и развития «Спектр». – 2022. – Т. 7. – С. 9-17.

24. Макситдин о'гли Н.Ф., Шухратова А.Ф. ГРУППИРОВКА ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ПО СТЕПЕНИ РАЗВИТИЯ ПСИХИЧЕСКИХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ ЧЕЛОВЕКА //Научный репозиторий. – 2024. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 292-299.
25. Shuhratova A. F. PEDAGOGICAL METHODS FOR DEVELOPING SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS OF UNIVERSAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS. – 2024.
26. Норбугаев Ф. ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ УСЛОВИЯ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНТЕГРАТИВНОГО ПОДХОДА В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ БАЗОВЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ ОБЩЕГО СРЕДНЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ //Центральноазиатский журнал междисциплинарных исследований и исследований в области управления. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 49-53.
27. Норботаев Ф. ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ СТУДЕНТОВ КАК СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА //Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 103-107.
28. Норботаев Ф. М. ОСНОВНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТНОГО ПОДХОДА //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMİY JURNALI. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 5. – С. 78-82.